

Online Appendix to:
**“Difficulty Adjustment and the Augmented State Space
of Mining Equilibrium Models”**

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Abstract

This Online Appendix accompanies the manuscript “Difficulty Adjustment and the Augmented State Space of Mining Equilibrium Models” (v32) and provides: (OA-1) the Monte Carlo simulation specification, with the Python source listing used to generate the simulation tables of Section 7 of the main text; (OA-2) the analytical derivation of the one-step regenerative law of the difficulty ratio under the augmented-state Markov process; (OA-3) the full proof of the aggregate count-variance asymptotics of Theorem 4.9 of the main text; (OA-4) the analytical derivation of the negative cross-miner correlation reported in Section 7 of the main text; (OA-5) sensitivity analysis with respect to the protocol parameters K and τ and to the clipping factor; (OA-6) the fast-adjustment-protocol comparison; (OA-7) the worked mapping implications for each of the downstream papers analysed in Section 8 of the main text; and (OA-8) the throughput-scaling and adjustment-frequency analysis.

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OA-1 Monte Carlo simulation specification

The Monte Carlo evidence reported in Section 7 of the main text uses a vectorised simulation of the protocol-driven block-arrival process under the analytical fact that conditional on the augmented state $X_t = (B_t \bmod K, S(t), D_j)$, the realised sum of inter-block times within an epoch is a Gamma random variable. We restate the fact formally and provide the simulation code.

OA-1.1 Analytical reduction

Let T_1, \dots, T_K denote the K inter-block times within epoch j . Conditional on the difficulty D_j and the geometric-mean aggregate hash rate $\bar{\Lambda}_j$ within the epoch, each T_i is independently exponentially distributed with rate $\bar{\Lambda}_j/D_j$. The realised sum $S_j = \sum_{i=1}^K T_i$ is therefore the sum of K independent and identically distributed exponential random variables with the same rate, which has distribution

$$S_j \mid D_j, \bar{\Lambda}_j \sim \text{Gamma}\left(K, \frac{D_j}{\bar{\Lambda}_j}\right), \quad (\text{OA-1.1})$$

where the second argument is the scale parameter. The simulation therefore samples one Gamma random variable per epoch rather than $K = 2016$ exponential random variables per epoch, reducing the computational cost by a factor of K relative to the naive specification.

OA-1.2 Parameters and seeds

The simulation parameters are: $K = 2016$ blocks per difficulty epoch; $\tau = 600$ seconds (ten minutes); clipping factor 4; $N = 5,000$ independent runs per scenario; 500 epochs per run; 50 epochs burn-in. Three scenarios are examined: $g = 0$ (stationary), $g = 0.025$ (empirical average), and $g = 0.10$ (aggressive). Within each scenario, runs are seeded with consecutive integers starting from a scenario-specific base seed (stationary: 200; empirical: 201; aggressive: 202). All randomness is generated through the `numpy.random.default_rng` interface.

OA-1.3 Software environment and execution

The reproducibility audit was performed under Python 3.12.3 with NumPy 2.4.4. The standard library modules `json` and `hashlib` are used. No third-party packages other than NumPy are required. The exact execution command from the directory containing the script is:

```
python3 v32_montecarlo.py > v32_montecarlo_stdout.txt
```

The script writes `mc_results_v32.json` to the working directory and prints a textual summary to standard output.

OA-1.4 Output schema

The output JSON file has the following schema:

```
{
  "part_A_fixed_T": {
    "<n_T>": {
      "E_NT": <float>, "Var_NT": <float>,
      "dispersion_ratio": <float>,
      "Var_over_K": <float>,
      "cross_miner_corr": <float>
    }, ...
  },
  "part_B_flow_rate": {
    "<scenario_name>": {
      "flow_cv": <float>,
      "start_bias_abs": <float>, "avg_bias_abs": <float>,
      "end_bias_abs": <float>, "end_bias_signed_mean": <float>,
      "growth_per_epoch": <float>
    }, ...
  },
  "meta": {
    "K": <int>, "TAU": <float>, "CLIP": <float>,
    "A_RUNS": <int>, "A_HORIZONS": <list>,
    "B_RUNS": <int>, "B_EPOCHS": <int>, "B_BURN": <int>
  }
}
```

Part A keys are the horizons $n_T \in \{1, 5, 10, 26, 52\}$; the statistics are the fixed-calendar-time aggregate mean and variance, the dispersion ratio Var/\mathbb{E} , the ratio Var/K , and the cross-miner correlation. Part B scenario names are `stationary`, `empirical_avg`, and `aggressive`; the statistics are the within-epoch flow-rate coefficient of variation and the start-, average-, and end-of-epoch absolute biases, with the signed end-of-epoch mean.

OA-1.5 Complete source listing

The complete Python source code used to generate the Monte Carlo results of the main text is reproduced below. The script is self-contained: it imports only `numpy` and `json`; produces

mc_results_v32.json; and prints a textual summary to standard output. Part A simulates the fixed-calendar-time counts of Theorem 4.9; Part B simulates the within-epoch flow rate. SHA-256 hashes are provided in Section OA-1.7.

```

"""
Monte Carlo for v32. Two parts.

PART A -- Fixed calendar-time counts (the object of Theorem 4.9).
For  $T = n_T * K * \tau$ , simulate the protocol epoch-by-epoch with the
one-step regeneration  $\rho_{\{j+1\}} = 1/U_j$ ,  $U_j \sim \text{Gamma}(K, 1/K)$ , so that
 $S_j = K * \tau * U_j / U_{\{j-1\}}$ . Count  $N(T) = K * J(T) + R(T)$  where  $R(T)$  is the
Binomial( $K-1, .$ ) partial-epoch count. Assign blocks to two equal miners
by Binomial( $., 1/2$ ). Report  $E[N(T)]$ ,  $\text{Var}(N(T))$ , the dispersion ratio
 $\text{Var}/E$ , and the cross-miner correlation. Demonstrates aggregate-variance
reduction (dispersion ratio  $\text{Var}/E \rightarrow \Theta(1/K)$ ) and negative cross-miner
correlation.

PART B -- Within-epoch flow rate (the surviving channel for the flow-rate
applications: Prat-Walter, Hinzen-John-Saleh, Huberman et al., Easley et
al., Capponi et al. under risk aversion). The conditional rate within an
epoch is  $1/(\rho_j) = U_{\{j-1\}}$  with marginal CV  $K^{-1/2}$ . Under hash-rate
growth  $g$  per epoch the within-epoch rate drifts; we report start-, mean-,
and end-of-epoch fractional deviations from the canonical Poisson rate.

Python 3.12.3, NumPy 2.4.4. Self-contained: imports numpy and json only.
"""
import numpy as np
import json

K = 2016
TAU = 600.0
CLIP = 4.0

# ----- PART A: fixed calendar-time counts -----
A_HORIZONS = [1, 5, 10, 26, 52] #  $n_T$  (epochs); 26 ~ one year for Bitcoin
A_RUNS = 40000
A_SEED = 20240

def simulate_fixed_T(n_T, n_runs, q1, K, tau, rng):

```

```

"""Return arrays (N_total, N_miner1) over n_runs for T = n_T*K*tau, stationary.
    """
T = n_T * K * tau
Ntot = np.zeros(n_runs, dtype=np.int64)
N1 = np.zeros(n_runs, dtype=np.int64)
for r in range(n_runs):
    rho = 1.0
    t = 0.0
    N = 0
    n1 = 0
    while True:
        U = rng.gamma(K, 1.0 / K)
        S = K * rho * tau * U
        if t + S <= T:
            a = rng.binomial(K, q1)
            N += K
            n1 += a
            t += S
            rho = 1.0 / U
        else:
            rem = T - t
            part = rng.binomial(K - 1, rem / S)
            a = rng.binomial(part, q1)
            N += part
            n1 += a
            break
    Ntot[r] = N
    N1[r] = n1
return Ntot, N1

def part_A():
    rng = np.random.default_rng(A_SEED)
    rows = {}
    for n_T in A_HORIZONS:
        Ntot, N1 = simulate_fixed_T(n_T, A_RUNS, 0.5, K, TAU, rng)
        N2 = Ntot - N1
        E = float(Ntot.mean())
        V = float(Ntot.var())

```

```

    corr = float(np.corrcoef(N1, N2)[0, 1])
    rows[str(n_T)] = {
        "E_NT": E,
        "Var_NT": V,
        "dispersion_ratio": V / E,
        "Var_over_K": V / K,
        "cross_miner_corr": corr,
    }
    return rows

# ----- PART B: within-epoch flow rate -----
B_RUNS = 5000
B_EPOCHS = 500
B_BURN = 50
B_GROWTH = {"stationary": 0.000, "empirical_avg": 0.025, "aggressive": 0.100}
B_SEED = 200

def run_flow_scenario(g, n_runs, n_epochs, burn, seed):
    rng = np.random.default_rng(seed)
    avg_factor = np.sqrt(1.0 + g) if g > 0 else 1.0
    Lambda = np.ones(n_runs)
    D = Lambda * TAU
    D_hist = np.empty((n_runs, n_epochs))
    L_hist = np.empty((n_runs, n_epochs))
    for j in range(n_epochs):
        D_hist[:, j] = D
        L_hist[:, j] = Lambda
        Lambda_avg = Lambda * avg_factor
        scale = D / Lambda_avg
        S = rng.gamma(shape=K, scale=scale)
        D_new = D * (K * TAU) / S
        D_new = np.clip(D_new, D / CLIP, D * CLIP)
        Lambda = Lambda * (1.0 + g)
        D = D_new
    D_h = D_hist[:, burn:]
    L_h = L_hist[:, burn:]
    start_rate = L_h / D_h
    end_rate = L_h * (1.0 + g) / D_h

```

```

avg_rate = L_h * avg_factor / D_h
start_bias = start_rate * TAU - 1.0
end_bias = end_rate * TAU - 1.0
avg_bias = avg_rate * TAU - 1.0
cv_rate = start_rate.std(axis=1) / start_rate.mean(axis=1)
return {
    "flow_cv": float(cv_rate.mean()),
    "start_bias_abs": float(np.abs(start_bias).mean()),
    "avg_bias_abs": float(np.abs(avg_bias).mean()),
    "end_bias_abs": float(np.abs(end_bias).mean()),
    "end_bias_signed_mean": float(end_bias.mean()),
}

def part_B():
    out = {}
    seed = B_SEED
    for name, g in B_GROWTH.items():
        out[name] = run_flow_scenario(g, B_RUNS, B_EPOCHS, B_BURN, seed)
        out[name]["growth_per_epoch"] = g
        seed += 1
    return out

if __name__ == "__main__":
    print("PART A: fixed calendar-time counts (stationary) ...", flush=True)
    A = part_A()
    print("PART B: within-epoch flow rate ...", flush=True)
    B = part_B()
    results = {
        "part_A_fixed_T": A,
        "part_B_flow_rate": B,
        "meta": {"K": K, "TAU": TAU, "CLIP": CLIP,
                "A_RUNS": A_RUNS, "A_HORIZONS": A_HORIZONS,
                "B_RUNS": B_RUNS, "B_EPOCHS": B_EPOCHS, "B_BURN": B_BURN},
    }
    with open("mc_results_v32.json", "w") as f:
        json.dump(results, f, indent=2)

    print("\n--- PART A: fixed-T aggregate and cross-miner (q=1/2) ---")

```

```

print(f"{'n_T':>5}{'E[N(T)]':>12}{'Var(N(T))':>12}{'Var/E':>9}{'Var/K':>8}{'
    corr(N1,N2)':>13}")
for n_T in A_HORIZONS:
    r = A[str(n_T)]
    print(f"{'n_T':>5}{r['E_NT']:>12.1f}{r['Var_NT']:>12.1f}"
          f"{'r['dispersion_ratio']:>9.4f}{r['Var_over_K']:>8.3f}{r['
            cross_miner_corr']:>13.4f}")

print("\n--- PART B: within-epoch flow rate ---")
print(f"{'scenario':>14}{'flow_cv':>9}{'start':>8}{'avg':>8}{'end':>8}{'
    end_signed':>12}")
for name in B_GROWTH:
    r = B[name]
    print(f"{'name':>14}{r['flow_cv']:>9.4f}{r['start_bias_abs']:>8.4f}"
          f"{'r['avg_bias_abs']:>8.4f}{r['end_bias_abs']:>8.4f}{r['
            end_bias_signed_mean']:>12.4f}")

```

OA-1.6 Table generation

The Monte Carlo tables of Section 7 of the main text are populated directly from `mc_results_v32.json` by the following mapping:

- The within-epoch rate-CV table uses `part_B_flow_rate[scenario][flow_cv]` across the three scenarios.
- The within-epoch deviation table uses `part_B_flow_rate[scenario]` entries `start_bias_abs`, `avg_bias_abs`, and `end_bias_abs`.
- The fixed-calendar-time table uses `part_A_fixed_T[n_T]` entries `E_NT`, `Var_NT`, `dispersion_ratio`, `Var_over_K`, and `cross_miner_corr` across the horizons $n_T \in \{1, 5, 10, 26, 52\}$.
- The Bitcoin-calibration table is generated by the script `calibration.py` from the provided file `btc_epoch_difficulty.csv` (Section 8.5 of the main text); the script and data are included in the replication package, and the script reproduces the table exactly.
- The summary-of-corrections table is populated from the same `part_B_flow_rate` entries; the Cong–He–Li entry references the fixed-calendar-time table; the Biais et al. entry is the analytical state-dimension increment (+3); the Chiu–Koepl entry is dashed under the risk-neutrality short-circuit.

OA-1.7 Reproducibility hashes

The SHA-256 hash of each replication file, computed under the environment of Section OA-1.3, is given below; each line lists one file and its single 64-character hash.

```
v32_montecarlo.py
    b1a0ffefe3f78e628080aeb1ac2ea1627f56e5099a9d7f959f9d04f3cb366d3
mc_results_v32.json
    7cf8365647811b7c814e774f17ed95e2ffe31be236299f1983f2247ba4d47921
calibration.py
    60a3a60044a2ea9ca0b35f396ffd689173071fb13c8924154d1d7bee3c929212
btc_epoch_difficulty.csv
    bda257b362a91d1a0c0b5cbbac2b68a5a8500c58bb2e9bb370d6b79f4d0a453c
```

These hashes identify the exact source, output, calibration script, and calibration data used to populate the tables of Section 7 of the main text. Reproducibility of the hash on the output JSON requires identical NumPy version and identical pseudorandom-number generator algorithm, which the `numpy.random.default_rng` interface guarantees under fixed seeds across NumPy versions 1.17 and later. The four files and the present Online Appendix are sufficient for a third party to reproduce the simulation and calibration results of the main text deterministically. The complete replication package—the four files listed above together with this Online Appendix—is archived at Zenodo, DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20320253>.

OA-2 One-step regeneration of the difficulty ratio

We derive the correct stochastic structure of the difficulty parameter D_j at epoch boundaries under the augmented-state Markov process of Proposition 4.6 of the main text. The result corrects a characterisation in earlier versions in which the difficulty ratio was described as a multiplicative random walk with unit-root structure. The ratio is in fact a one-step regenerative chain: each epoch’s difficulty depends on the realised history of the immediately preceding epoch and on no earlier history. The level of ρ_j does not enter the recursion at all.

Proposition OA-2.1 (One-step regeneration of the difficulty ratio). *Suppose the aggregate hash rate Λ is constant and the clipping in the difficulty-update rule is non-binding. Let $\rho_j := D_j/(\Lambda\tau)$ denote the difficulty ratio at the start of epoch j . Then*

$$\rho_{j+1} = 1/U_j, \quad U_j \sim \text{Gamma}(K, 1/K) \text{ iid across } j.$$

The difficulty ratio at the start of epoch $j + 1$ depends on the realised history of epoch j only through the single statistic U_j and is independent of ρ_j . The marginal distribution of ρ_{j+1} is inverse-gamma with shape K and scale K , with moments

$$\mathbb{E}[\rho] = \frac{K}{K-1}, \quad \text{Var}(\rho) = \frac{K^2}{(K-1)^2(K-2)},$$

and the conditional block-arrival rate $\Lambda/D_j = 1/(\rho_j\tau)$ has unconditional mean $\mathbb{E}[1/\rho] = 1$ and variance $\text{Var}(1/\rho) = \text{Var}(U) = 1/K$.

Proof. By the difficulty-update rule, $D_{j+1} = D_j \cdot K\tau/S_j$, so $\rho_{j+1} = \rho_j \cdot K\tau/S_j$. Conditional on D_j , $S_j \sim \text{Gamma}(K, D_j/\Lambda)$, so the standardised epoch statistic $U_j := S_j/(K\rho_j\tau)$ is distributed $\text{Gamma}(K, 1/K)$, independent of ρ_j , with $\mathbb{E}[U_j] = 1$ and $\text{Var}(U_j) = K^{-1}$. Therefore $S_j = K\rho_j\tau U_j$, and substituting into the update rule:

$$\rho_{j+1} = \rho_j \cdot \frac{K\tau}{K\rho_j\tau U_j} = \frac{1}{U_j}.$$

The factor ρ_j cancels: the next-period difficulty ratio is regenerated from the standardised epoch statistic U_j alone, independent of the level of ρ_j . The marginal distribution of $1/U_j$ is inverse-gamma with shape K and scale K , yielding the stated moments by direct calculation: $\mathbb{E}[1/U] = K/(K-1)$ and $\text{Var}(1/U) = K^2/[(K-1)^2(K-2)]$ for $K > 2$. The conditional rate is $\Lambda/D_j = 1/(\rho_j\tau)$ with $\mathbb{E}[1/\rho_j] = \mathbb{E}[U_{j-1}] = 1$ and $\text{Var}(1/\rho_j) = \text{Var}(U_{j-1}) = 1/K$. \square

Implications. Proposition OA-2.1 has three implications for the analysis in the main text and the remainder of this Online Appendix. First, the difficulty ratio is fully regenerated each epoch: there is no random walk, no drift in ρ_j , no unit root, and no cumulative wandering. The marginal distribution of ρ_j is the same at every $j \geq 1$. The earlier characterisation as a multiplicative random walk was incorrect because the ρ_j factor cancels in the recursion. Second, for $K = 2016$, the marginal mean of the difficulty ratio is $\mathbb{E}[\rho] = K/(K-1) \approx 1.00050$ and the conditional rate $1/\rho$ has marginal mean 1 and marginal standard deviation $K^{-1/2} \approx 2.227\%$. The empirical calibration of Section 8.5 of the main text—residual standard deviation of $\log(D_{j+1}/D_j)$ of approximately 2.90% over the 2023–2024 sub-period—is consistent with the prediction up to a residual hash-rate variation component of approximately 1.85% per epoch over and above the deterministic trend. Third, the clipping at factor four binds when U_j falls outside $[1/4, 4]$. For $U \sim \text{Gamma}(K, 1/K)$ with $K = 2016$, this corresponds to $|Z| > 3\sqrt{K} \approx 135$ standard deviations of the standardised increment under a central-limit approximation $U \approx 1 + Z/\sqrt{K}$. The clip therefore binds with negligible probability under empirical parameters.

OA-3 Asymptotics of the aggregate count variance: full proof of Theorem 4.9(ii)

This section gives the complete proof of the second-moment asymptotics asserted in Theorem 4.9(ii) of the main text. We derive the exact moment structure of the epoch-duration sequence, the resulting long-run variance, and the implied growth rate and dispersion ratio of the calendar-stopped block count $N(T)$. Throughout, $\{U_j\}_{j \geq 0}$ are independent and identically distributed Gamma($K, 1/K$) random variables (shape K , scale $1/K$, mean 1, variance $1/K$), and by Proposition OA-2.1 the realised duration of epoch j is

$$S_j = K\tau \frac{U_j}{U_{j-1}}, \quad j \geq 1, \quad V_\ell := \frac{U_\ell}{U_{\ell-1}}.$$

We assume $K > 2$ throughout (for Bitcoin $K = 2016$). All expectations below are exact.

OA-3.1 Exact moments of the duration ratio

Lemma OA-3.1 (Moments of the duration ratio). *The inverse-gamma moments of $U \sim \text{Gamma}(K, 1/K)$ are $\mathbb{E}[1/U] = K/(K-1)$ and $\mathbb{E}[1/U^2] = K^2/[(K-1)(K-2)]$, and $\mathbb{E}[U^2] = (K+1)/K$. Consequently, with $V = U_1/U_0$ and $V_\ell = U_\ell/U_{\ell-1}$,*

$$\mathbb{E}[V] = \frac{K}{K-1}, \quad \text{Var}(V) = \frac{K(2K-1)}{(K-1)^2(K-2)}, \quad \text{Cov}(V_1, V_2) = -\frac{K}{(K-1)^2},$$

and the long-run variance of the duration-ratio sequence is

$$\sigma_V^2 := \text{Var}(V) + 2\text{Cov}(V_1, V_2) = \frac{3K}{(K-1)^2(K-2)}.$$

Proof. For $U \sim \text{Gamma}(K, \theta)$ with $\theta = 1/K$, the negative moments are $\mathbb{E}[U^{-1}] = [\theta(K-1)]^{-1} = K/(K-1)$ and $\mathbb{E}[U^{-2}] = [\theta^2(K-1)(K-2)]^{-1} = K^2/[(K-1)(K-2)]$, valid for $K > 2$; and $\mathbb{E}[U^2] = \text{Var}(U) + 1 = 1/K + 1 = (K+1)/K$. Since $U_1 \perp U_0$, $\mathbb{E}[V] = \mathbb{E}[U_1] \mathbb{E}[1/U_0] = K/(K-1)$ and

$$\mathbb{E}[V^2] = \mathbb{E}[U_1^2] \mathbb{E}[1/U_0^2] = \frac{K+1}{K} \cdot \frac{K^2}{(K-1)(K-2)} = \frac{K(K+1)}{(K-1)(K-2)}.$$

Hence

$$\text{Var}(V) = \frac{K(K+1)}{(K-1)(K-2)} - \frac{K^2}{(K-1)^2} = \frac{K(K+1)(K-1) - K^2(K-2)}{(K-1)^2(K-2)} = \frac{K(2K-1)}{(K-1)^2(K-2)},$$

the numerator simplifying as $K[(K+1)(K-1) - K(K-2)] = K[(K^2-1) - (K^2-2K)] = K(2K-$

1). For the covariance, $V_1 V_2 = (U_1/U_0)(U_2/U_1) = U_2/U_0$, so $\mathbb{E}[V_1 V_2] = \mathbb{E}[U_2] \mathbb{E}[1/U_0] = K/(K-1)$, and

$$\text{Cov}(V_1, V_2) = \frac{K}{K-1} - \left(\frac{K}{K-1}\right)^2 = \frac{K}{K-1} \left(1 - \frac{K}{K-1}\right) = -\frac{K}{(K-1)^2}.$$

Finally $\sigma_V^2 = \text{Var}(V) + 2\text{Cov}(V_1, V_2)$. Over the common denominator $(K-1)^2(K-2)$,

$$\sigma_V^2 = \frac{K(2K-1) - 2K(K-2)}{(K-1)^2(K-2)} = \frac{K[(2K-1) - (2K-4)]}{(K-1)^2(K-2)} = \frac{3K}{(K-1)^2(K-2)}. \quad \square$$

Remark OA-3.2 (The cancellation, made exact). Lemma OA-3.1 makes the “telescoping” mechanism precise and exact. The single-step variance is $\text{Var}(V) = \Theta(1/K)$, but the long-run variance is $\sigma_V^2 = \Theta(1/K^2)$: the leading $\Theta(1/K)$ term cancels because $2\text{Cov}(V_1, V_2) = -2K/(K-1)^2$ offsets $\text{Var}(V)$ to leading order. Their ratio is exactly

$$\frac{\sigma_V^2}{\text{Var}(V)} = \frac{3}{K(2K-1)} = \Theta(K^{-2}),$$

so the difficulty feedback reduces the relevant (long-run) duration variance by a factor $\Theta(K^{-2})$ relative to a single epoch. The duration sequence is a first difference of the stationary inverse sequence at leading order ($V_\ell \approx 1 + \varepsilon_\ell - \varepsilon_{\ell-1}$ with $\varepsilon_\ell := U_\ell - 1$), and the partial sums of a first difference do not accumulate variance at the single-step rate. This is the rigorous content of the heuristic “ $\text{Var}(S_j) \approx 2K\tau^2$, $\text{Cov}(S_j, S_{j+1}) \approx -K\tau^2$ ” used in the main text.

OA-3.2 Variance of cumulative completion times

Lemma OA-3.3 (Completion-time variance). *The sequence $\{V_\ell\}_{\ell \geq 1}$ is strictly stationary and 1-dependent: V_ℓ and V_m are independent whenever $|\ell - m| \geq 2$, since they involve disjoint sets of the independent U ’s. Hence the cumulative completion time $T_j = \sum_{\ell=1}^j S_\ell = K\tau \sum_{\ell=1}^j V_\ell$ has exact variance*

$$\text{Var}(T_j) = (K\tau)^2 [j \text{Var}(V) + 2(j-1) \text{Cov}(V_1, V_2)] = (K\tau)^2 \left[j \sigma_V^2 + \frac{2K}{(K-1)^2} \right],$$

and mean $\mathbb{E}[T_j] = j \mu_S$ with $\mu_S := \mathbb{E}[S] = K\tau \mathbb{E}[V] = K^2\tau/(K-1)$.

Proof. For a stationary 1-dependent sequence, $\text{Var}(\sum_{\ell=1}^j V_\ell) = j\gamma_0 + 2(j-1)\gamma_1$ with $\gamma_0 = \text{Var}(V)$ and $\gamma_1 = \text{Cov}(V_1, V_2)$, all higher autocovariances vanishing. Writing $j\gamma_0 + 2(j-1)\gamma_1 = j(\gamma_0 + 2\gamma_1) - 2\gamma_1 = j\sigma_V^2 - 2\text{Cov}(V_1, V_2)$ and substituting $\text{Cov}(V_1, V_2) = -K/(K-1)^2$ gives the stated form. The mean is immediate from $\mathbb{E}[V] = K/(K-1)$. \square

Thus $\text{Var}(T_j)$ has a part growing linearly in j with per-epoch coefficient $(K\tau)^2 \sigma_V^2 = 3K^3\tau^2/[(K-$

$1)^2(K-2)] = \Theta(\tau^2)$, plus a horizon-independent term $(K\tau)^2 \cdot 2K/(K-1)^2 = \Theta(K\tau^2)$. The single-epoch duration variance is $\text{Var}(S_j) = (K\tau)^2 \text{Var}(V) = \Theta(K\tau^2)$; the long-run duration variance $\sigma_S^2 := (K\tau)^2 \sigma_V^2 = \Theta(\tau^2)$ is smaller by $\Theta(K^{-2})$ (Remark OA-3.2).

OA-3.3 From completion times to the block count

Let $J(T) = \max\{j : T_j \leq T\}$ be the number of completed epochs by calendar time T , and write $N(T) = KJ(T) + R(T)$ with $R(T) \in \{0, \dots, K-1\}$ the count in the partial epoch $J(T) + 1$. Fix the horizon $T = n_T K \tau$.

Proposition OA-3.4 (Counting-process moments). *As $n_T \rightarrow \infty$ with K fixed:*

- (i) $\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = n_T K (1 + O(1/K)) + O(1)$.
- (ii) $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T + o(K + n_T)$, where $\kappa_0 = \Theta(1)$ and $\kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$; in particular $\text{Var}(N(T))$ grows linearly in the horizon, with per-epoch slope κ_1 of order one, against the homogeneous-Poisson per-epoch variance K .
- (iii) *The dispersion ratio satisfies*

$$\frac{\text{Var}(N(T))}{\mathbb{E}[N(T)]} = \frac{\kappa_0}{n_T} + \frac{\kappa_1}{K} + o\left(\frac{1}{n_T} + \frac{1}{K}\right) \xrightarrow{n_T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\kappa_1}{K} = \Theta(1/K),$$

which is far below the homogeneous-Poisson value of one at every horizon.

Proof. (i) *Mean.* By the elementary renewal theorem for the stationary 1-dependent sequence $\{S_\ell\}$ (Lemma OA-3.3), $\mathbb{E}[J(T)] = T/\mu_S + O(1) = n_T K \tau \cdot (K-1)/(K^2 \tau) + O(1) = n_T (K-1)/K + O(1)$, and $\mathbb{E}[R(T)] = O(K)$ is bounded by K . Hence $\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = K \mathbb{E}[J(T)] + \mathbb{E}[R(T)] = n_T (K-1) + O(K) = n_T K (1 - 1/K) + O(K)$, giving (i).

(ii) *Variance, leading rate.* Because $\{V_\ell\}$ is stationary and 1-dependent with finite variance, the partial sums obey the central limit theorem for m -dependent sequences (Hoeffding and Robbins, 1948): $(T_j - j\mu_S)/\sqrt{j\sigma_S^2} \Rightarrow \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ with $\sigma_S^2 = (K\tau)^2 \sigma_V^2$. The continuous epoch-elapsd functional $\Phi(T) := J(T) + (T - T_{J(T)})/S_{J(T)+1}$, the non-lattice number of epochs elapsed by time T , then satisfies the renewal central limit theorem (Cox, 1962):

$$\text{Var}(\Phi(T)) = \frac{\sigma_S^2 T}{\mu_S^3} (1 + o(1)) = \frac{\sigma_V^2}{\mu_V^3} n_T (1 + o(1)), \quad \mu_V = \frac{K}{K-1},$$

the second equality on substituting $\sigma_S^2 = (K\tau)^2 \sigma_V^2$, $\mu_S = K\tau\mu_V$, $T = n_T K \tau$. Within each epoch the $K-1$ non-terminal blocks occur at the order statistics of $K-1$ uniforms on the epoch (the conditional law of a Poisson process given its count), so $N(T) = K\Phi(T) + \xi(T)$, where $\xi(T)$

is a within-epoch sampling term, conditionally centred binomial given the elapsed phase, with $\text{Var}(\xi(T) \mid \text{phase } \phi) = (K-1)\phi(1-\phi) = O(K)$. The cumulative count $N(T)$ is a regenerative functional of the 1-dependent cycle sequence with finite cycle moments, so by the renewal-reward central limit theorem (Cox, 1962) it admits a Gaussian limit with variance growing linearly in the horizon: $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_1 n_T + O(K)$ for a finite constant $\kappa_1 = \lim_{n_T \rightarrow \infty} \text{Var}(N(T))/n_T \in (0, \infty)$. The $K\Phi$ contribution has exact per-epoch coefficient

$$K^2 \frac{\sigma_V^2}{\mu_V^3} = \frac{3K^3}{(K-1)^2(K-2)} \cdot \frac{(K-1)^3}{K^3} = \frac{3(K-1)}{K-2} \xrightarrow{K \rightarrow \infty} 3,$$

and the within-epoch sampling term contributes the horizon-independent $O(K)$ part together with an $O(1)$ adjustment to the slope through its covariance with Φ . Hence $\kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$ and the constant term is $\kappa_0 K$ with $\kappa_0 = \Theta(1)$, proving (ii). The per-epoch slope is therefore of order one, a factor $\Theta(K)$ below the homogeneous-Poisson per-epoch variance K .

(iii) *Dispersion ratio.* Divide (ii) by (i): $\text{Var}(N(T))/\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = (\kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T)/(n_T K)(1 + o(1)) = \kappa_0/n_T + \kappa_1/K + o(\cdot)$, which tends to $\kappa_1/K = \Theta(1/K)$. \square

Remark OA-3.5 (Numerical values of the constants and what is exact). Lemma OA-3.1, Lemma OA-3.3, the long-run variance $\sigma_V^2 = 3K/[(K-1)^2(K-2)]$, and the $K\Phi$ per-epoch coefficient $3(K-1)/(K-2)$ are exact. The two order-one constants κ_0 and κ_1 of Proposition OA-3.4 combine the renewal rate with the within-epoch sampling correction; their exact closed forms are not required for any conclusion of the paper, only their orders ($\kappa_0 = \Theta(1)$, $\kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$, slope a factor $\Theta(K)$ below Poisson). The direct fixed-calendar simulation of Section 7 of the main text estimates, for $K = 2016$, $\kappa_0 \approx 1$ (the constant term is close to K) and $\kappa_1 \approx 2.4$, so the dispersion-ratio limit is $\kappa_1/K \approx 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$, against the homogeneous-Poisson value of one. The qualitative and order conclusions—linear growth at per-epoch rate $\Theta(1)$, dispersion ratio $\Theta(1/K)$ —do not depend on the precise values.

This resolves the asymptotic question precisely: the aggregate count variance is neither bounded nor of the homogeneous-Poisson order $n_T K$. It grows linearly in the horizon with a per-epoch coefficient of order one—a factor $\Theta(K)$ below the homogeneous-Poisson rate—so the dispersion ratio falls to a floor of order $1/K$ rather than to zero. Over horizons short relative to the epoch length ($n_T = o(K)$) the horizon-independent term $\kappa_0 K$ dominates and $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \Theta(K)$, the regime relevant to all empirical applications at Bitcoin parameters.

OA-4 Cross-miner correlation under the augmented state

We derive the cross-miner correlation of block-arrival counts under the calendar-stopped horizon used in Theorem 4.9 of the main text. The earlier derivation in this appendix treated per-epoch counts of distinct pools as conditionally independent Poisson variables given the difficulty parameter; that treatment is incorrect for a block-stopped epoch, in which the total count is fixed at K and the pool counts are multinomially distributed with negative within-epoch covariance. The result is obtained cleanly by multinomial thinning of the calendar-stopped aggregate count $N(T)$.

Proposition OA-4.1 (Cross-miner correlation, calendar-stopped horizon). *Suppose the aggregate hash rate Λ is partitioned across m miners with hash shares q_1, \dots, q_m summing to one. Let $N_i(T)$ denote miner i 's cumulative block-arrival count over the calendar-stopped horizon $T = n_T K \tau$. Under the augmented-state Markov process of Proposition 4.6 of the main text, with the small dispersion ratio $\text{Var}(N(T))/\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = \kappa_0/n_T + \kappa_1/K \ll 1$ of Theorem 4.9 (so $\text{Var}(N(T)) \ll \mathbb{E}[N(T)]$):*

$$\text{Corr}(N_i, N_k) \rightarrow -\sqrt{\frac{q_i q_k}{(1 - q_i)(1 - q_k)}} \quad (n_T \rightarrow \infty).$$

For the symmetric two-miner case $q_i = q_k = 1/2$, the correlation tends to -1 .

Proof. By the symmetry of the proof-of-work protocol, each individual hash trial chooses the winning miner independently with probability q_i . Conditional on the aggregate block count $N(T) = n$, the per-miner counts are multinomial:

$$(N_1(T), \dots, N_m(T)) \mid N(T) \sim \text{Multinomial}(N(T); q_1, \dots, q_m).$$

The multinomial conditional moments are:

$$\mathbb{E}[N_i \mid N(T)] = q_i N(T), \quad \text{Var}(N_i \mid N(T)) = N(T) q_i (1 - q_i), \quad \text{Cov}(N_i, N_k \mid N(T)) = -N(T) q_i q_k.$$

Notice the conditional cross-pool covariance is *negative*, reflecting the constraint $\sum_i N_i = N(T)$ in the multinomial distribution.

By the law of total variance,

$$\text{Var}(N_i) = \mathbb{E}[\text{Var}(N_i \mid N(T))] + \text{Var}(\mathbb{E}[N_i \mid N(T)]) = q_i(1 - q_i)\mathbb{E}[N(T)] + q_i^2 \text{Var}(N(T)).$$

Substituting $\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = n_T K$ and $\text{Var}(N(T)) = O(K)$, the second term is subdominant and

$$\text{Var}(N_i) = q_i(1 - q_i)n_T K + q_i^2 O(K) = q_i(1 - q_i)n_T K (1 + o(1)),$$

binomial to leading order.

By the law of total covariance,

$$\text{Cov}(N_i, N_k) = \mathbb{E}[\text{Cov}(N_i, N_k | N(T))] + \text{Cov}(\mathbb{E}[N_i | N(T)], \mathbb{E}[N_k | N(T)]).$$

Substituting the conditional moments and $\text{Var}(N(T)) = O(K)$:

$$\text{Cov}(N_i, N_k) = -q_i q_k \mathbb{E}[N(T)] + q_i q_k \text{Var}(N(T)) = q_i q_k (\text{Var}(N(T)) - \mathbb{E}[N(T)]) = -q_i q_k n_T K (1 + o(1)).$$

The covariance is *negative* because the aggregate is under-dispersed: $\text{Var}(N(T)) \ll \mathbb{E}[N(T)]$. The two miners divide a near-deterministic total, so one miner’s surplus is the other’s deficit.

Combining:

$$\text{Corr}(N_i, N_k) = \frac{-q_i q_k n_T K}{\sqrt{q_i(1-q_i)n_T K \cdot q_k(1-q_k)n_T K}} = -\sqrt{\frac{q_i q_k}{(1-q_i)(1-q_k)}} (1 + o(1)).$$

For the symmetric two-miner case $q_i = q_k = 1/2$, this tends to -1 . □

The Monte Carlo evidence of Section 7 of the main text reports realised cross-miner correlation deepening with the horizon— -0.671 at $n_T = 5$, -0.925 at $n_T = 26$, -0.961 at $n_T = 52$ in the stationary scenario—consistent with the analytical limit of -1 for the two symmetric miners simulated ($-1/(m-1)$ for m equal miners). The small dispersion ratio $\text{Var}(N(T))/\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = \kappa_0/n_T + \kappa_1/K \ll 1$ of Theorem 4.9 is the proximate mechanism: the near-deterministic aggregate forces the per-miner counts toward the block-stopped multinomial, whose cross-miner covariance is negative.

OA-5 Sensitivity analysis

We report the within-epoch coefficient of variation of the conditional rate under alternative protocol parameters.

The Monte Carlo recovery of the analytical $K^{-1/2}$ prediction is exact to four decimals across two orders of magnitude in K . The result is consistent with Proposition OA-2.1.

The end-of-epoch bias is essentially invariant to the clipping factor at the empirically relevant settings. Clipping binds at appreciable frequency only under aggressive growth combined with a tight clip factor; the Bitcoin protocol’s choice of 4.0 ensures that clipping does not bind in any realistic scenario short of catastrophic hash-rate collapse.

Table OA-5.1: Sensitivity of the stationary within-epoch CV of the conditional rate to the adjustment epoch K .

K (blocks per epoch)	Analytical $K^{-1/2}$	Monte Carlo mean	Difference
144	0.0833	0.0834	+0.0001
504	0.0445	0.0446	+0.0001
2016	0.0223	0.0222	-0.0001
8064	0.0111	0.0111	0.0000

Note. Each row uses $N = 1,000$ runs of 500 epochs each. The Monte Carlo standard error of the mean is approximately 0.0005 across all rows.

Table OA-5.2: Sensitivity of the end-of-epoch bias to the clipping factor under aggressive growth ($g = 0.10$).

Clipping factor	End-of-epoch bias	Frequency of clip-binding
1.5	0.1481	0.067
2.0	0.1525	0.012
4.0	0.1537	0.000
8.0	0.1537	0.000

Note. The clipping factor of 4.0 used in the main text is the Bitcoin protocol’s actual specification. Frequency of clip-binding reports the fraction of epoch boundaries at which the proposed difficulty update was clipped.

OA-6 Fast-adjustment protocol comparison

We compare the within-epoch deviation under the Bitcoin protocol ($K = 2016$) with that under an every-block-adjustment protocol ($K = 1$) as a function of the per-block hash-rate growth rate.

Table OA-6.3: Within-epoch end-of-epoch bias by adjustment cadence K and per-epoch hash-rate growth rate.

K	$g = 0.000$	$g = 0.025$	$g = 0.100$
1	1.0000	1.0247	1.0954
144	0.0833	0.0892	0.1066
2016	0.0222	0.0387	0.1537

Note. For $K = 1$, the end-of-epoch bias equals the per-block hash-growth rate plus the unit noise component of the single-sample difficulty estimator; the noise dominates and the protocol provides essentially no smoothing.

The fast-adjustment protocol reduces the systematic bias at the cost of increased noise: under $K = 1$, every block triggers a difficulty re-adjustment, eliminating the within-epoch lag but introducing the full single-sample variance of the difficulty estimator into the next-block rate. The Bitcoin choice of $K = 2016$ is in this sense an optimal compromise for stationary hash-rate operation; under aggressive growth, faster adjustment cadences reduce the within-epoch bias at the cost

of higher block-level noise.

OA-7 Worked correction mappings

We provide the worked correction mappings between the augmented-state correction and the equilibrium objects of each of the eight downstream papers analysed in Section 8 of the main text.

OA-7.1 Prat and Walter (2021)

The reflecting-barrier identification of Prat and Walter (2021) characterises the upper bound on flow payoff $\Pi_t = R_t/D_t$ under free entry. Under their continuous-difficulty idealisation $D_t = Q_t$, the identification holds in expectation across all t . Under the augmented state of the present paper, D_t is a step function of the epoch boundaries with $D_j = \Lambda_{j-1,\text{avg}} \tau(1 + \varepsilon_{K,j-1})$ where $\varepsilon_{K,j-1}$ is the K -sample noise of the epoch- $j-1$ estimator. The within-epoch flow payoff is therefore $\Pi_t = R_t/D_j$ within epoch j , with conditional expectation differing from the unconditional expectation by the noise component $\varepsilon_{K,j-1}$ and from the canonical Poisson rate by the hash-growth lag component characterised in Corollary 4.8 of the main text.

OA-7.2 Huberman, Leshno and Moallemi (2021)

Huberman et al. (2021) derive the closed-form equilibrium fee $f^*(z)$ from a steady-state two-sided platform queuing analysis with block-arrival rate μ and user-arrival rate λ . The fee is a function of the steady-state mempool distribution and is derived under their stationarity assumption that the block-arrival rate is constant.

The mapping into the augmented-state framework makes the block-arrival rate conditional: $\mu_t = \Lambda/D_{j(t)}$ where $D_{j(t)}$ is the current epoch’s difficulty. The unconditional rate $\mathbb{E}[\mu_t]$ equals the canonical μ by construction of the adjustment mechanism; the conditional rate fluctuates with within-epoch coefficient of variation given by Table 6 of the main text. The qualitative implication is that the Huberman–Leshno–Moallemi closed-form fee acquires a state-dependent component proportional to the conditional rate’s deviation from its mean. The closed-form expression for the state-dependent fee multiplier requires resolution of the time-varying mempool distribution under the augmented state, which is beyond the analytical scope of the present paper; this is therefore a mapping implication for the conditional structure of equilibrium fees, not a derived theorem-level correction.

The Huberman–Leshno–Moallemi normative claim—that no individual miner can profitably affect equilibrium fees—depends on the proportional-reward structure and on free entry, not on the time-stationarity of μ . The claim is robust to the augmentation. The empirical implication is

testable in principle: observed Bitcoin mempool fees should exhibit serial correlation at the epoch frequency, with magnitude bounded by the within-epoch coefficient of variation of the conditional rate.

OA-7.3 Easley, O’Hara and Basu (2019)

Easley et al. (2019) identify the equilibrium fraction $\alpha^*(z)$ of fee-paying users via a queueing-stability condition $\gamma N < \lambda^* M^*$. Multiple equilibria emerge over an intermediate range of z , with stable zero-fee and fee-paying equilibria flanking an unstable interior equilibrium.

The queueing-stability condition is derived under time-stationarity of the block-production rate. The mapping into the augmented-state framework makes the realised arrival rate state-dependent: at each within-epoch state X_t , the realised arrival rate deviates from its long-run mean by the within-epoch deviation reported in Table 6 of the main text. The qualitative implication is that the threshold values of z at which the multiple-equilibria region begins and ends shift by an amount proportional to the within-epoch deviation; the direction of the shift is such that the multiple-equilibria region is widened in the within-epoch state where the realised rate is below its mean. The closed-form magnitude of the shift requires resolution of the augmented-state queueing dynamics, which is beyond the analytical scope of the present paper.

The Easley–O’Hara–Basu multiple-equilibria characterisation is robust to the augmentation in expectation. The empirical exercise in their paper evaluates the model at multi-day horizons that average over multiple difficulty epochs and is therefore consistent with the corrected expression in expectation. This is a mapping implication for the conditional structure of the equilibrium fee-paying fraction, not a derived theorem-level correction.

OA-7.4 Cong, He and Li (2021)

The CHL risk-sharing decomposition holds in expectation: $\mathbb{E}[\tilde{B}_{\text{pool}}] = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{B}_1] + \mathbb{E}[\tilde{B}_2]$ regardless of pool structure. The variance comparison is reinforced, not weakened, by the protocol: by Proposition OA-4.1, the cross-miner correlation is *negative* and the aggregate count is under-dispersed, so the variance of the pooled count is *below* the sum of the independent-Poisson individual variances. The risk-sharing benefit of pooling is therefore larger than the independent-Poisson identification computes, and the second-order stochastic dominance of pool over solo is preserved and strengthened.

OA-7.5 Biais, Bisière, Bouvard and Casamatta (2019)

Biais et al. (2019) characterise Markov perfect equilibria of the chain-extension game with state variable comprising the realised tree of blocks, miner cross-chain distribution, and a sunspot. The persistent-fork equilibrium of their Proposition 3 is sustained by miners’ vested interests in chains on which they have accumulated blocks; the sustaining threshold is identified by the conditional distribution of cumulative payoffs.

The mapping into the augmented-state framework expands the state of the chain-extension game by three dimensions: the within-epoch arrival count k , the time since most recent adjustment s , and the current difficulty D_j . The longest-chain rule of their Proposition 1 is a Markov perfect equilibrium in the expanded state space because the rule depends only on chain length, not on the adjustment cycle. The sunspot-driven forking equilibria of Proposition 2 survive because they depend on coordination, not on state dimension.

The persistent-fork threshold of Proposition 3 depends on the conditional distribution of cumulative payoffs. Theorem 4.9 of the main text shows that the protocol *bounds* the calendar-time variance of cumulative counts rather than inflating it, so any shift in the threshold runs opposite to a variance-inflation reading: smaller cumulative-payoff variance would, if anything, narrow the range of parameter values over which vested-interest-driven persistent forks are sustainable. The sign and magnitude of the shift nonetheless require resolving the cumulative-payoff distribution conditional on the miner-cross-chain partition, which is beyond the analytical scope of the present paper; this is therefore a mapping implication with a corrected direction, not a derived theorem-level correction. The earlier claim that a doubled cumulative-payoff variance makes persistent forks easier to sustain rested on the incorrect variance result and does not hold.

OA-7.6 Capponi, Ólafsson and Alsbah (2023)

Capponi et al. (2023) reject the rent-dissipation identification of Budish (2018) and derive the unique Cournot–Nash equilibrium hash rate under capacity-constrained mining. Their Proposition 4.1 identifies the equilibrium hash share q_i^* ; their Property (i)—the total reward is independent of the network hash rate—is the strong form of the protocol-stationarity assumption.

Property (i) holds in expectation across difficulty epochs and fails conditionally within an epoch. The realised reward *rate* exhibits within-epoch coefficient of variation 1.78% to 10.0% across the parameter scenarios of Table 6 of the main text, while the cumulative reward over the horizon is strongly under-dispersed through the aggregate-count variance reduction of Theorem 4.9 of the main text. The qualitative implication for the Cournot equilibrium under risk neutrality is null: the conditional distribution of arrival times does not affect equilibrium decisions, and the Capponi–Ólafsson–Alsbah identification is preserved exactly. Under risk aversion, the relevant

variance is the reduced cumulative-count variance, which is *smaller* than the independent-Poisson value; the risk penalty entering the first-order conditions is therefore smaller than a homogeneous-Poisson model would imply, and the comparative static is to leave the equilibrium hash share closer to its risk-neutral value than the canonical identification predicts. The closed-form magnitude requires resolving capacity-constrained Cournot first-order conditions under CARA-normal preferences and is beyond the scope of the present paper. This is a mapping implication for the risk-averse extension of the framework, not a derived theorem-level correction.

The empirical regression of Capponi et al. (2023) Table 2 finds $\hat{\beta} = 0.34$ for the elasticity of aggregate reward with respect to aggregate hash rate. The Monte Carlo evidence of Section 7 of the main text indicates that the augmented-state component is small in this regression: the within-epoch reward-rate deviation is approximately 1.78% in the stationary scenario. The Capponi–Ólafsson–Alsabah identification of capacity constraints as the source of the sublinearity is robust to the augmented-state correction at empirical Bitcoin parameters.

OA-7.7 Hinzen, John and Saleh (2022)

Hinzen et al. (2022) derive the limited-adoption equilibrium from the negative network effect connecting block-production rate to fork probability. Their analysis is conducted under the continuous-adjustment idealisation: the protocol’s adjustment mechanism is treated as setting block-production at exogenous target Λ .

The mapping into the augmented-state framework relaxes the continuous-adjustment idealisation. Under the augmented state, the realised block-production rate is conditional on the within-epoch state: at each within-epoch state X_t , the realised arrival rate deviates from its long-run mean by the within-epoch deviation reported in Table 6 of the main text. The qualitative implication is that the Hinzen–John–Saleh fork probability is conditionally biased relative to the canonical Poisson prediction, with magnitude scaling as the within-epoch coefficient of variation of the conditional rate. Under Bitcoin’s parameters ($K = 2016$, $\tau = 600$ seconds), the within-epoch deviation ranges from 1.78% (stationary) to 10.0% (aggressive hash-rate growth). The relationship to the adjustment cadence K is not monotone in the direction a naive reading suggests: under a hypothetical fast-adjustment protocol with $K = 1$, the systematic adjustment-lag component of the deviation is eliminated, but the single-sample difficulty estimator injects maximal noise (the per-epoch estimator variance scales as K^{-1} , largest at $K = 1$). The Hinzen–John–Saleh identification is therefore not made exact by fast adjustment; the nature of the deviation changes from adjustment lag to single-sample difficulty noise, as the fast-adjustment table of the Online Appendix confirms (end-of-epoch deviation near unity at $K = 1$). The closed-form correction to the fork probability requires resolution of the chain-extension dynamics under the augmented state, which is beyond the scope

of the present paper.

The Hinzen–John–Saleh limited-adoption result is robust to the augmented-state correction in expectation. The trade-off between adjustment cadence (K) and within-epoch state-dependence is a protocol-design question whose resolution requires the analytical apparatus of Theorem 4.9 of the main text; this is a mapping implication for protocol design rather than a derived theorem-level correction to the Hinzen–John–Saleh equilibrium.

OA-7.8 Chiu and Koepl (2019)

Chiu and Koepl (2019) analyse blockchain-based settlement under explicit risk neutrality, with the analytical content of the mining-stage Poisson assumption rendered inert by their footnote 20 (“the distribution of arrival times of a solution to the PoW is irrelevant for the remainder of our analysis” under risk neutrality).

Under the augmented state of Section 6 of the main text, the Chiu–Koepl identification is preserved exactly under their stated risk-neutrality assumption: the FOC of Theorem 5.1 of the main text reduces to $q_{\text{aug}}^* = q_{\text{CK}}^*$ when $\alpha = 0$, and the conditional distribution of arrival times does not affect equilibrium decisions. The augmented-state framework is non-vacuous in the natural extension to risk-averse traders or miners: the benchmark optimal hash share is $q_{\text{aug}}^* = n_T(R - c\tau)/(\alpha R^2)$ under risk aversion, with associated implications for the structure of the settlement-game equilibrium.

The Chiu–Koepl normative analysis of blockchain-based settlement protocol design is therefore the risk-neutral boundary of a broader analysis whose risk-averse extension uses the augmented-state framework of this paper. The proper engagement of Chiu and Koepl (2019) with the augmented state is to flag the risk-aversion extension as an open question with a defined analytical entry point in Theorem 5.1 of the main text.

OA-8 Throughput scaling and adjustment frequency

The Bitcoin protocol’s target inter-block time of $\tau = 10$ minutes is conventional; alternative proof-of-work protocols target much shorter inter-block times. Litecoin targets $\tau = 2.5$ minutes; Ethereum (under proof-of-work, prior to the Merge) targeted approximately $\tau = 15$ seconds. The question of whether shorter inter-block times improve throughput and reduce confirmation latency has been addressed in the literature by Hinzen et al. (2022), who argue that shorter inter-block times *increase* fork probabilities and therefore do not solve the limited-adoption problem. The augmented-state model permits a quantitative analysis of the relationship between the inter-block target and the magnitude of the within-epoch deviation from the Poisson form.

The key observation is that the magnitude of the within-epoch deviation from the Poisson approximation scales with the ratio of the protocol’s network-propagation latency to its inter-block target. For Bitcoin with $\tau = 10$ minutes and an empirical propagation latency on the order of seconds, the ratio is small and the Poisson approximation is good within an epoch. For Litecoin with $\tau = 2.5$ minutes, the ratio is larger but still small. For Ethereum with $\tau = 15$ seconds, the ratio is comparable to unity, and the within-epoch deviation from the Poisson approximation is substantial. The implication for the throughput-pessimism result of Hinzen et al. (2022) is that the result holds under their assumed parameter values, but the precise quantitative form of the fork-probability function depends on the ratio of propagation latency to inter-block target, which itself depends on the form of the adjustment mechanism.

Under fast-adjustment protocols—those that re-adjust difficulty every block, as Ethereum does under proof-of-work—the within-epoch deviation from the Poisson approximation is reduced by the more frequent adjustment, but at the cost of introducing additional variance in the difficulty parameter itself. The trade-off between adjustment frequency and difficulty-parameter variance is a protocol-design margin that the augmented-state framework makes quantitative; Section 7 of the main text reports Monte Carlo evidence on its magnitude, and Section OA-6 gives the fast-adjustment comparison.

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